

The Dirac Delta Variation on Varying Lorentz Manifolds

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the meaning of the Dirac delta function in the new framework of the 8 – theory. In this framework, a moderate amount of flexibility is given using the delta. It is a delta variation. The Dirac function is associated with propagation of fermion fields. Those fields appear at any time, not just at t=0. We find the Dirac delta as a vital part for a sufficient description of nature.

The following variation is different from the original function of Dirac as it has more flexibility concerning the element of time. The variation require that delta function will appear at time, which is not null as well. That is equivalent to excitements on quantum field theories.

Introduction

Our two main equations in the framework:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial g'}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

The Dirac delta in our framework is an interference on the Lorentzian manifold. An arbitrary amount of curvature δg on the manifold. Since it is not allowed and must vanish, we require $\delta g = 0$, as we did previously in this framework.

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t > 0 \quad (4)$$

So the Dirac delta in our framework describe the process in which arbitrary amount of curvature appear, and vanish into matter. However, there is no restriction with regard to time. arbitrary amount of Curvature can appear at any time, so we must modify the idea Of the Dirac in our framework.

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t) + \Delta t \quad (6)$$

We also require that $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ as just after the arbitrary amount or interference will appear, it will immediately vanish into matter. So in this framework is rich in delta functions. The difference is that the delta can appear at time that is not null. In a sense, we have more flexibility with the delta.

After the delta appeared and as a result fermions were manifested into the metric. Those fermions could still vary, and experience a net curvature or net variation as was analyzed In the thesis. Those net curvatures were taken to be prime numbers and that was the reasoning behind the construction of the coupling constant equation.

Those net variations of the manifold are another interference, but and interference which propagate from fermions, and is prime number. Therefore, in that sense it cannot turn into fermions. **Fermions vanish in even amount of variations.** The result is a propagation across the manifold Ripples on the metric all across.

$$\delta g = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t_1 = Q(t) + \Delta t \quad (7)$$

At later continuation of time:

$$t_2 > t_1 \quad (8)$$

This condition is satisfied:

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t_2 = Q(t) + \Delta t + \Delta t \quad (9)$$

And the amount of variations is either prime or one.

$$\delta g = 2 \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) \text{ for } n > 1$$

$$\delta g = 1$$

Then we have a ripple on the manifold which propagate all across, toward all directions The Laplacian operator than is vital to description for a mathematical description of the manifold ripples, or bosonic fields.

The most important point to take is that the **underlining reason for the boson propagation all across the metric is their prime number feature**. They could not vanish into matter. moreover, based on this framework we cannot associate a morphism between a boson ripple fields and fermions interferences, super symmetry is not possible in this framework. A bosonic ripple across the Lorentzian Metric:

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2 M(x)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(y)}{\partial^2 g} + \frac{\partial^2 M(z)}{\partial^2 g} \quad (10)$$

That is curvature propagation across all metric spatial dimensions as:

$$M(x, y, z) \in S \quad (11)$$

$$S = (M, g) \quad (12)$$

Therefore, in this framework, that is the difference between fermion fields, associated with even amount of variations, and bosonic fields, with prime amount of variations. We analyzed the difference in this paper by using the Dirac delta function.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)